

Policy Brief

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The Impact of European Border Externalization on Humanitarian Aid and Access in the Sahel Region

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Key Points

- The externalisation of migration control has involved extensive outsourcing of migration control powers and resources outside of European territory, as well as shifting responsibilities to transit states and international organisations.
- Due to the increased presence of international and European organisations in the Sahel region, migrants perceive them to be part of this migration control agenda.
- Migrants in transit in Niger and Mali linked their lack of trust in humanitarian organisations to perceptions that they work with the police to deport them or seek to prevent them from migrating.
- The erosion of trust in and refusing of aid makes it more difficult for organisations to provide relevant support and access potential beneficiaries, which in turn increases protection gaps.

Background

In recent years, the Sahel region has attracted the attention of European Union (EU) policymakers aiming to prevent the onward travel of Europe-bound migrants. The cooperation with countries of transit and origin has involved extensive outsourcing of migration control powers and resources outside of European territory, as well as shifting responsibilities to transit states and international organisations. This externalisation refers to a wide range of practices from direct or remote controls of borders, and rescue operations, to measures addressing the drivers of migration and improving and widening return policies and programmes. As such, it blurs the lines between humanitarian aid, development assistance, border control and security interventions. In some cases, such as in Niger, the cooperation on migration and border management has led to a legislative change criminalising the transport of migrants in the country.

Therefore, in contexts where migrants are facing increased risks along the routes towards the EU, humanitarian actors are called upon to play a bigger role in responding to migrants' greater vulnerabilities and protection needs. At the same time, the outsourcing of such externalized intervention to international and non-governmental (humanitarian) organisations may lead to increased suspicion and perceived risks of transit migrants towards these organizations. This policy brief analyses one of the repercussions of these interventions, namely the reduced trust of migrants in transit towards humanitarian organisations and in turn the policy implications for the humanitarian system. It discusses the possible impacts and repercussions of external control interventions on migrant safety and on the ability of humanitarian organisations to provide protection in contexts of vulnerable migration situations.

The process of externalization in the Sahel and the role of international organisations

There is increasing evidence of the negative impact that the externalization of EU migration control policies have had on migrants stranded in transit countries. As noted by Phillips and Missbach (2017: 141), the longer people “linger in limbo, the more vulnerable they become to economic and other forms of exploitation.” Migrants face increased physical risks as they are forced to take more dangerous routes and to stay in more hidden accommodations with no access to external support leading in turn to increased humanitarian needs.

Textbox 1: European externalisation policies not only rely on the active cooperation from countries of transit and origin to adopt specific legislative and policy measures, but migration-related activities in these countries have been increasingly delegated to humanitarian and development organisations.

In Agadez and Gao, humanitarian organisations are involved in external migration control in different capacities and by taking on various roles. While some organisations are purely involved in, for example, providing medical assistance, other organisations, the IOM and UNHCR being the most prominent, are involved in a mix of humanitarian protection, border and migration politics (Moretti, 2020). This is in line with the trend of humanitarian programming in the region having become more ‘migration-targeted’ (Frowd, 2018).

Key findings

The qualitative analysis of 90 interviews¹ with migrants in transit in Agadez, Niger and Gao, Mali has produced the following results: First of all, mistrust is shaped by the perceived risks of humanitarian and development organisations’ involvement in migration control. Secondly, a lack of trust leads to not accessing aid as a strategy to avoid perceived risks (i.e., deportation, exploitation, safety risks).

Mistrust in humanitarian organisation as a risk-assessment on a risky journey

Humanitarian organisations have been entrusted by European donors with more funding, competencies and a division of tasks with regards to migration-related humanitarian programming. Consequently, the study shows that migrants’ perception of an organisation’s mandate and involvement in the migration control system impacts their trust in these organisations. The perceived collaboration between organisations and national police or governments and the belief that accessing services would expose migrants to risks, most

¹ The data was collected from December 2020 to February 2021 by the Independent Monitoring, Research and Evidence Facility (IMREF) SSS Phase II programme commissioned by the Foreign, Commonwealth, and Development Office (FCDO). It was delivered by a consortium led by Integrity Global, which includes Seefar, IMPACT Initiatives, and Danube University Krems. Data was collected by Seefar.

notably deportation to their countries of origin, plays the most important role in shaping mistrust:

Textbox 2: “As soon as migrants suspect that organizations follow government directives and help discourage applications for migration, mistrust will become great. People will try anything to get to their destinations, which will promote clandestine and criminal practices.” (Female migrant in Gao, Mali)

This supports the general claim in the literature on migration and border control, that stricter control measures do not limit migration but rather redirect it and make journeys more dangerous (Molenaar and Ezzedinne, 2019; Phillips and Missbach, 2017). Furthermore, there is a high degree of awareness amongst migrants of information and return campaigns, who is behind them and with what intention. When asked what humanitarian and development organisations can do to increase trust in them, a respondent in Agadez, Niger said:

Textbox 3: “Organisations should respect their [humanitarian] commitment and to do their work properly, and they should avoid wasting their time with awareness-raising on the risks of migration because we are fully aware of the risks, and we are responsible for our own choices.” (Male migrant in Agadez, Niger)

In both Agadez and Gao, respondents believed that the European Union funds humanitarian organisations to stop respondents from migrating. This confirms findings from Carling and Hernández-Carretero (2011) that in many Sub-Saharan countries there is a widespread awareness of European desires to limit African migration to Europe and the campaigns are interpreted in this light.

Vulnerabilities and Protection Gaps created through migration-control induced mistrust

When migrants do not trust an organisation, this may exacerbate vulnerable situations when they decide not to access organisations in times of need. Vulnerabilities may be linked to physical and mental health, lack of financial resources, discrimination and risk of exploitation, gender-based violence and other rights violations.

Textbox 4: The decreased trust in humanitarian organisations is a repercussion of the externalisation of migration control and creates a protection gap among those travelling on routes from West to North Africa.

Limited trust and reticence to access organisations often means that migrants wait until they are extremely vulnerable before seeking support. For instance, a 22-year-old Cameroonian female returnee in Agadez explained that she approached organisations “when she found herself in a situation of absolute despair” after being expelled from Algeria. Key informants agreed that returnees, who have often lost all their belongings and funds, were more likely to approach them than migrants on their first journey. As a result, they are unable to provide migrants with information on how to avoid harm as they travel northward, or with items to prepare for their journeys more safely (e.g. adequate clothes, hygiene kits).

The findings point to the relevance of perceptions in protection outcomes, especially in politicised environments of migration control. There were clear differences between Niger and Mali, which suggests that contextual differences between the two locations influence attitudes towards humanitarian organisations. Interviewees in Niger drew a direct link between their lack of trust in authorities and the criminalisation of migration to a much larger extent than they did in Mali, and often attributed it to the law 2015-36 on the criminalisation of the transport of migrants. This supports previous findings concerning the spill-over effects of external migration management on for example the hindrance of free movement within the ECOWAS region (Bisong, 2020).

Policy Implications

The literature and empirical data on border externalization provide evidence for the various and diverging implications of external interventions on local contexts and on migrants’ journeys. This policy brief emphasizes why it is important to look at how migrants perceive externalisation and associated risks, as migrant perceptions play a key role in their decision-making while they navigate humanitarian support. This then has implications for humanitarian actors, donors and migration policy makers. The following briefly discusses some policy recommendations:

Accounting for the adverse consequences of externalized migration control and outsourcing to humanitarian actors

The continuous interventions by EU and other international actors in countries of origin and transit of migrants in Africa has far reaching consequences for global migration governance. By involving humanitarian organisations in a containment agenda, EU states and donors may actually hinder and complicate their work, as they are perceived by migrants as the “long arm” of such policies and not as neutral actors providing aid and protection. This is especially evident when organisations implement awareness raising campaigns and return programmes. When the work of an organisations becomes too involved in migration control, migrants may not seek their help anymore. National governments and donors should therefore take this into account.

In addition to creating exacerbated vulnerable situations for migrants, mistrust and the externalisation of migration control therefore poses a problem for the work of humanitarian actors

International humanitarian and development organisations have started to take trust seriously in their access strategies as well as criticizing the pressure put on them by donors to implement a migration containment agenda (Red Cross' EU Office, 2021). It is essential for organisations to pay attention to the negative effects of migrant-targeted programming and continuously reflect on their ambiguous role in bordering, the donors they engage with, and the messages they send to migrants and related communities. In turn, donors should consider ways to enhance their roles in ensuring accountability to beneficiaries.

Support a holistic and localised approach to humanitarian and development aid

“Mainstreaming” migration governance and migrant protection in humanitarian and development work without overly emphasizing the border security aspect. Furthermore, programming should take into account local socio-economic implications and designing humanitarian programming so that it supports the overall population. Donors should consider supporting not just the big, well-known organisations, but also the smaller local ones, as they are often able to work more directly with local and migrant populations.

Making protection and human security a priority in migration governance

In line with the 2018 Global Compact for Migration (GCM) and the European Commission's 2020 New Pact for Migration and Asylum and its goals of facilitating “safe, orderly and regular migration”, the European Union and its member states should support initiatives which concretely work towards this goal. For example, according to IOM's Missing Migrants Project, more than 2,000 migrant deaths have been documented since 2014 in the Sahara Desert alone, but experts believe the numbers are higher. For states to truly engage in the support for saving migrant lives on their journeys, the support and funding of search and rescue missions in this area would be a vital strategy to save lives. Furthermore, the lobbying for and increasing the support for humanitarian resettlement programmes is a strategy to increase safe and regular migration.

Further Reading/References

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